

**EMPLOI DU PASSÉ COMPOSÉ
PAR LES APPRENANTS DU SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL AU GHANA /
USE OF THE PASSÉ COMPOSÉ
BY SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN GHANA**

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This article focuses on the difficulties encountered by Senior High School students in Ghana in using the present perfect tense (*passé composé*) in French. Our objective is to determine how students apply the radical, inflexion, auxiliaries and past participle of this tense in their oral and written communications. A particular attention is given to its semantic aspects, especially how the *passé composé* conveys meanings related to pure actions, processes, continuity, subject and attribute, existence of the subject, and transitions from one state to another.